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Pratham Partha: The Narrative of Battle Within

Dr Arpita Mitra

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
S. M. College, Tilkamanjhi Bhagalpur University.

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Abstract:

Pratham Partha (1960), a verse narrative by Budhdhadeb Basu is a nuanced portrayal of one of most tragic characters of Indian mythology. In this work, Basu's poetic prowess has given voice to Karna's inner psyche through his one to one episodic encounters with his biological mother Kunti, then Draupadi and finally Sri Krishna. Basu portrays Karna in this poetic drama as a deeply wounded person inside who is haunted by a sense of betrayal. He seeks recognition for his valour but finds himself a victim of social injustice for being a representative of the lower caste people. After his conversations with Kunti and Draupadi, he feels betrayed by the two women whom he wished to love most intensely in his life. His meeting with Krishna leaves him more disillusioned. Here, Krishna is stripped of his divinity and has been reduced to a political figure whose only concern is the well - being of the Pandavas, especially of Arjuna who has accepted his unquestionable authority and political supremacy like a blind follower. In this narrative, Sri Krishna is not the merciful saviour of all. On the other hand Karna, the hero of this narrative, eventually succeeds to establish himself as a true warrior who is determined to participate in the Kurukshetra war with a stern sense of duty, dedication and loyalty. Though he becomes aware of his inevitable death in an unfair battle with Arjuna, he does not waver for a

moment . Here, Karna adheres to the dharma or duty (the key concept discussed in the epic Mahabharata) by refusing to switch side and remains firm in his decision to fight without any expectation of the results.

Keywords: Verse Narrative, Social Injustice, Politics, Duty, Warrior, Battle.

Budhdhdeb Basu (1908-1974) is considered a versatile genius in the twentieth century Bengali literature after Rabindranath Tagore. Though he is generally referred to as a poet, he wrote several novels, short stories, plays, essays besides poetry. He was an eminent critic and editor of his time. While teaching Indo- European Epics (included in Comparative Literature Curriculum of Indiana University in USA) he decided to explore Mahabharata from a newer perspective. His verse narratives including *Pratham Partha* (1960) are reinterpretations of the epic *Mahabharata* from an avant garde perspective. This newer and broader vision of the epic was developed by the inputs of his students in Indiana University as well as due to a re examination of other works on Mahabharata by earlier Indian scholars .

Pratham Partha is a nuanced portrayal of one of the most tragic and intriguing characters of Indian mythology, Karna who is a born warrior, but has been treated lifelong as a charioteer's son. He is virtuous but he has chosen the side of the Kauravas. *Pratham Partha* is a textual attempt to reconstruct the character of Karna. Basu provides his readers with a new understanding to reinterpret the character of Karna. Tagore too did it earlier in his verse drama *Karna Kunti Sambad* (1900). Basu followed Tagore while portraying Karna and at the same time he carved a trajectory of his own by incorporating Greek elements into this play and exploring the character of Karna through the theory psychoanalysis. The old men present in the narrative, represent the chorus whose comments on the characters help the readers to understand the

motivations and actions of the personas in a better way. The protagonist, Karna mirrors Achilles, the Homeric hero in some respects. Karna's inherent hatred against Arjuna is actually “a change or reversal of content of love into its opposite instinct” (Freud 133). Love and hate as coexisting forces have been thoroughly analyzed within the periphery of this poetic play. The transformation of Karna’s love into hate results in a troubled psyche in Karna who remains basically alone and feels like a misfit throughout his life. Basu shows his deep insight as explores Karna’s psyche through his episodic encounters with his biological mother Kunti, then Draupadi and finally Sri Krishna. Basu portrays Karna here as a deeply wounded person inside who is haunted by the sense of betrayal and seeks recognition as a warrior. He also reinterprets “dharma” or duty from a broader context through Karna’s sense of duty. Karna in this text acts as a representative of the people who belong to the lower strata of the society and due to that they are often ostracized and become victims of social injustice.

From the very beginning of the narrative, Basu establishes Karna as the hero of it. He is invincible for having an incredible military skill. That is why he is going to play the pivotal role in the Kurukshetra war. It is interesting to note that though the result of Kurukshetra war largely depends upon Karna, he is neither a Pandava nor a Kaurava and he is not going to fight in the war for any personal benefit. He is participating in the war because of his commitment only. He considers it his duty to fight for Duryodhana in the battle while remaining loyal to him during his crisis. The very existence of the Kauravas depends solely on Karna because no one of the seniors like Bhishma, Dronacharya or Kripacharya would fight wholeheartedly in the battle for Duryodhana. So, Karna is the only saviour and the main pillar of strength for the Kauravas. He is playing such an instrumental role in the war that the whole scenario would change if he switches side or decides to withdraw himself as Achilles did in the Trojan War. Without him, Duryodhana

would never show the courage to initiate the war. So, according to Basu, Karna's presence is a crucial deciding factor behind the war.

From the depiction of the old men, the readers come to know about his other heroic qualities. They describe Karna as someone extraordinary as he is devoid of those vices commonly found in alpha males at that period. He does not like to live a very luxurious life, he does not go to hunting for being entertained at the cost of killing innocent animals. He is not interested in women. He is known among people as a valiant warrior, a man of commitment with a golden heart and always a giver, exactly like the Sun God. He could be the best of friends and the worst of enemies. Physically, he bears the characteristics of a person who belongs to Khsatriya varna (caste), so, there are controversies regarding his birth anecdotes. From his conversations with Kunti, Draupadi and Sri Krishna, the readers get to know Karna more closely. Kunti addresses him as a "dharmatma" (truthful) like Yudhistir and one and only competitor of Arjuna as a warrior. She introduces herself, as the wife of King Pandu and the mother of the Pandavas. She gradually reveals that Karna is her eldest son and the Sun God is his father. She deftly tries to tempt him by giving him reassurance that if he takes side of the Pandavas, he would achieve anything he desires, even royal throne and Draupadi as his queen. Karna makes no attempt to hide his distaste for this proposal. He declares that his parents are and always will be the charioteer Adhirath and his wife Radha. He also gives a message of absolute equality and universal brotherhood when he says, "All of us are children of the Sun as he is the source of life on the earth. We all survive due to his presence and in that sense, all of us are his children, even a worm in the gutter is his child." Thus Karna does not accept Kunti as his mother, though he had long cherished desire to meet his biological mother at some point of his life. He tells that he is ready to respect her as a queen but can never forget that she discarded him just after his birth

as an unwanted child. She abandoned him afloat on the river and since then he has been floating like a rootless man who has no definite destination to reach. A gripping sense of loss, uncertainty and identity crisis have been his constant companions. Kunti cannot be forgiven by him as she did not try to save him and remained silent when all the elders in Hastinapur insulted him in the worst possible way for his proletariat background. On that day, Duryodhana came forward as his rescuer. He made Karna his ally and gave him the status of a king. He crowned Karna as the king of the state of Anga. Thus he became 'Angaraj Karna' and earned eligibility to compete with the princes of Hastinapur. He blatantly refuses Kunti and her proposal to join the Pandavas in the war while stating that he knows very well that Kunti has chosen to disclose his real identity by compulsion, not out of love for her eldest son. He tells her, "I belong to nobody, I do not claim anybody as mine and I am what I am, nothing else" (Basu 98). When Kunti urges him to choose between the right and the wrong in a rational way, he tells her that it is his duty to serve Duryodhana as he is the one who has given him his due respect and has treated him as his equal. Duryodhana befriended him when he was rejected by the Pandavas and the rest of royal court due to his low birth. So he cannot leave Duryodhana's side at this hour of need at any cost. Though he forgives his mother at the end of their conversation, he clarifies his stand. He refuses everything that Kunti offers. He tells her that he neither wants the kingdom, nor Draupadi as gifts from the Pandavas. He is a warrior and he has capability to capture the entire world and rule over it exercising his power. To him this world is a battle front and he would like to earn things by his might and prowess. When the two old men, along with Kunti remind him of his brotherly duty and appealed him to support Pandavas in the impending war Karna again gives a philanthropic message of universal brotherhood. He says that he does not go by the rule books or according to the religious scriptures, he only follows the path of humanity that teaches him to

look upon all human beings as equal as they are children of Manu, the first man and progenitor of the human race.

In the next part of the conversation, when Draupadi asks Karna why he is participating in the war if he does not wish anything for himself, Karna replies that he wants recognition as the greater warrior than Arjuna. Karna's desire for recognition stem from his deep seated insecurity regarding his identity and it led him to fight for Duryodhana whom he knew to be genuinely flawed. Karna harbored a deep resentment against Arjuna because in his past encounters with Arjuna, whenever he got opportunity to vie with Arjuna, he was humiliated. Karna was disallowed twice to compete with Arjuna: first, in the tournament for the celebration of the completion of the military training of the Pandavas and the Kauravas and then in Draupadi's swayamvara. So defeating Arjuna was key motivating factor for his participation in the war.

After his conversations with Kunti and Draupadi, Karna feels betrayed by these two women whom he wished to love most intensely in his life. He finds Kunti's desire to get him back as a part of war plan and not at all driven by any motherly affection.

Though Karna does not respond to Draupadi's coquetry and her appeal to remain neutral during the war, his passionate feelings for her in the narrative cannot be missed by the reader. Karna's intense emotion for princess Draupadi originates from several factors. Like all, he too admires her for her beauty and personality. But, unlike others, he empathizes with her for the injustice she had to suffer at the hands of the Pandavas, particularly during the infamous dice game. Though Draupadi considers Karna as her adversary, Karna does not hesitate to admit that he has spent uncountable sleepless nights thinking of her. Her thoughts have kept him restless and his unfulfilled desire to achieve Draupadi gets entangled with his personal quest for identity,

honour and justice. His desire for Draupadi can be perceived as a symbol of his longing for recognition and the dignity denied to him due to his social background.

At the end of their conversation Draupadi predicts that Kurukshetra war would ultimately bring about Karna's downfall and Karna prays for Draupadi's victory. He could understand that both of them were victims of the same patriarchal social system that deprived them from exercising their rights properly. The caste and gender shaped their destinies and led to their helplessness and sufferings. Karna could see that Draupadi's status was reduced to a pawn in the politics of powerful people despite the fact that she was a lady with exceptional personality, intelligence and mental strength. Draupadi's polyandrous marriage to the Pandavas, consequential objectification and humiliation were all products of social and political arrangements made by a male-dominated world that restricted her freedom and denied her agency. Karna's struggle against discrimination and Draupadi's fight against gender based violence illustrate how the social order obstructs individuals from reaching their full potential and inflict immense pain. Karna realized while Draupadi overlooked the reality that they had been victimized by a complex interplay of power in an unjust world. Karna is surprised to find out that Draupadi has come to dissuade him from participating in the war and offers her friendship in return. He mockingly tells her that he has never imagined in his wildest dream that he would ever get an opportunity to serve queen Draupadi by remaining just inactive. At the same time he aggrieves that he cannot grant her request and wishes if they could meet each other in some other realm without any conflict of power or misleading deception. Draupadi criticizes Karna for his desperation to join the war. Karna accepts that he is waiting eagerly to participate in the war because it would bring him the opportunity to end his quest for an identity. He hopes to establish himself as a greater warrior than Arjuna. His battle is not only against a particular

person. It is against a hegemony which constantly pushes away the marginal people. Karna wants to dispel the identity of that outcast who can never be an equal to Prince Arjuna.

At the last phase of the narrative, Sri Krishna appears. He appreciates Karna that he has not joined the fruitless meeting where terms and conditions of the war have been finalized. It was implicit that according to Krishna, "fair is foul and foul is fair" in war. He knew that Karna was going to fight in the war without any political motivation. Ironically, it is Karna (rather than Arjuna) who is willing to fight the battle without any utilitarian purpose. Karna was among the few ones who participated in the war to fulfill duty. Krishna expresses his disappointment for the fact that Kunti and Draupadi's meetings yield no result as they could not dissuade him from fighting. On the other hand, Karna says that their encounters have not failed. For him it was an opportunity of lifetime to meet the ladies, one is his mother and the other one his dream woman. He feels grateful to these two ladies for letting him forget about the uncertainties for the time being. This confession of Karna reveals his pure heartedness in contradiction to Krishna's diplomacy. The conversation between Karna and Krishna establishes Karna as the ultimate idol of this narrative as well as the epic instead of Krishna. At the onset of this narrative Basu hints at Krishna's shrewdness. The fact that Krishna has been a politician beyond compare was disclosed during conversation of the two old men. In the final section of the narrative (conversation between Karna and Krishna) they again express their apprehension that Krishna may not play a very fair role in this entire business of war as he is devious by nature. Karna, on the contrary, lays his heart bare to Krishna because like most of the people he believes in Krishna's benevolence. He discloses his suppressed desire to lead a sheltered and an uninterrupted blissful family life like other people who are not driven by the urge of proving themselves like him. But at the next moment he is haunted by the fact that his life is meant for greater struggles.

Krishna also expresses his admiration and respect for his steadfastness, strength of character to stick by his decision up to the end. In reply Karna says that he believes that the merciless war would give him the meaning to his life and that it would be unbiased as well. Then Krishna accuses him of inviting destruction for the millions of innocent people because Duryodhana can dare to compete with Pandavas as long as Karna supports him. If Karna withdraws himself from the war or join the side of Pandavas then Duryodhana will quit. Karna replies that he has not initiated the war, he is only fulfilling his duty by fighting for Duryodhana. Then Krishna plays his master card by inviting Karna to join with Pandavas to ensure their victory so that the war would not last long. Karna expresses his inability to betray Duryodhan even if his defeat is inevitable. He is not afraid of embracing defeat one more time because he has been habituated to bear with the pangs of loss throughout his life. Krishna says that a noble person like Karna can easily curb his ego to save the people from the hazards of the war. Karna replies that he also prays for the well being of the people but the Kurukshetra war is going to be his personal battle that would bring an end to his search for identity, acceptance, recognition and honour. It would be a journey towards self discovery. He only wishes to combat Arjuna in a one to one battle so that he can take test of his own military skills and strength against Arjuna. Krishna reminds him that Arjun is his own brother. Then Karna says that only death can bring them closer as brothers and can end their lifelong rivalry. At this point Krishna gives his verdict that Karna will be defeated by Arjuna. Karna says that it will be decided in the battle only. Krishna replies that he would never allow Arjuna to be defeated, he will ensure Arjuna's victory at any cost. He will manipulate Arjuna to kill Karna when he will be at the most vulnerable, most helpless juncture of his life. This disdainful prediction of Krishna utterly shocks Karna as well as the readers. But Krishna further declares that nothing can be expected to be fair in the foul game of war. That's

why he would not hesitate to be unfair during the war where he plays the mastermind and Arjuna is a mere follower of him. Then Karna realizes that Krishna would protect Arjuna even by unfair means. All his claims that he is worried of the consequences of the Kurukshetra war, about profuse bloodshed, squalor and mass destruction are misleading and he is concerned only about the well being of Pandavas, particularly that of Arjuna. Krishna tries to justify this unfairness and injustice to Karna by declaring him as the chosen one who would attain eternal glory and a permanent place in the hearts of the people. He also tries to convince Karna for the last time to reconsider his decision as switching side would ensure his kingship and union with his family that are not less tempting. But Karna was already on the path of no return as everything was predestined and no one can escape the almighty fate.

The narrative focuses on Karna's battle on two levels: his profound psychological battle due to existential crisis and his lifelong struggle against social injustice. Here, in this text, Karna is basically a lone figure who is uprooted from his origin. Though, he wholeheartedly loves his foster parents as he proudly claims to be their son and considers himself as one who belongs to the charioteer class of people, his exceptional physical features and outstanding qualities distinguish him among the populace. His regal bearing and expertise in archery testify to his birth in some aristocratic Kshatriya family. On the other hand, he has never been welcomed by the people whom he really belonged to. This sense of non belongingness shaped the entire life of Karna in a tragic way. Karna's life is an example of how people feel alienated in a society and worried for status due to social injustice. In feudal society status is determined by birth and there remains a little hope for the proletarians to move upwards in the social ladder. Despite having outstanding talent Karna failed to reach the heights of success that he genuinely deserved. In Basu's narrative Karna possesses greater qualities than Krishna who is revered for his wisdom

and intellect. Krishna himself and the two men representing the mass expressed his high regard for Karna for his honesty, generosity, steadfastness and overall greatness of character in the text. Through an ironic reversal in the epic Krishna was transformed into a suta, the charioteer of Arjuna and Karna fought till his last breath with unerring aim and stunning power against all odds for accomplishing his duty while encountering the confirmed defeat and unavoidable death like an ideal Kshatriya as exemplified in *Shreemad Bhagawat Gita*.

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